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ACTUAL TRENDS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT THE UNIVERSITY

Objective. Examined in the article is the importance and methods of implementing professionally oriented education in general, with greater detail on the example of teaching a foreign language to students for whom a foreign language is not the main specialty. One of the author's goals is to show the options for interaction between the university and employers to increase the effectiveness of training young specialists both in the main specialty and in a foreign language.

Methodology. Given are specific examples of various professionally oriented events that can be organized jointly with potential employers, with their direct participation in the educational process. Such forms of work as testing, contests of educational projects, English-language seminars, questionnaires of employers, foreign language classes, which are necessary for teaching students to implement business intercultural communication in future professional activities, are considered in more detail.

Scientific novelty. The author considered the methods of organizing professionally oriented events in a foreign language, which are effective tools for foreign language professional training of students. The peculiarity of these events is joint preparation and implementation of these forms of work by teachers and potential employers. Direct participation of potential employers in professional training of students has a powerful incentive for students that contributes to more effective professional and foreign language training.

Conclusions. For employers at the labor market, it is important that future specialists should not only know the basics of their future profession, but also possess a number of new skills that complement the professional competence of future specialists. The development of students' skills and abilities that are in demand in the labor market requires a non-standard, creative approach to the organization of training sessions and active implementation of a variety of educational activities. These events actualize students' creative abilities, form the skills to independent search for unique solutions, develop creative thinking, develop foreign language training, which are integral components of an up-to-date specialist's professional competence. The activation of vocationally-oriented training in the university ensures a close relationship and consistency of the educational process with the requirements of the labor market and is aimed at training highly qualified young professionals.

Key words: university, labor market, employers, professional training, culture-oriented assignments.

Higher education system is a social institution that trains specialists to meet the needs of the labor market. The quality of training of young professionals determines not only the efficiency of industrial enterprises, organizations and institutions, but also the productivity of the economic and social sectors of the region and country as a whole.

The purpose of this article is to identify the most relevant and effective ways of developing the professional competence of students in close cooperation with potential employers in the educational process. The author gives specific examples of educational activities for the intensification and diversification of professional training and retraining of students, conducted with the participation and in interaction with employers. Also, the examples of culture-orientated assignments are included in the article that can be used to train sociocultural skills of the students.

For employers of the labor market at present it is important that future specialists should not only know the basics of their future profession, but also possess a number of new skills that complement their professional competence. Employers note the importance of such components of professional competence as

the need for productive teamwork, the ability to present the created products, ideas and reports, conduct business negotiations, have stress resistance, the ability to manage time, and also work in the conditions of limited time. Regardless of the specialty and the acquired profession, at present, the labor market requires such competencies as: the ability to acquire new knowledge, the ability to improve in a new area of knowledge and professional activity, the ability to plan, organize and coordinate activities, openness to new opportunities, the ability to build interpersonal relationships, avoid disagreements in the work group or find ways to overcome conflict situations. Consequently, the development of students' skills and abilities that are in demand in the labor market requires a non-standard, creative approach to the organization of training sessions and active implementation of a variety of educational activities [6, 51–52]. It is extraordinary, non-traditional, creative educational events that actualize students' creative abilities, form their skills of independent search for unique solutions, develop creative thinking, which are integral components of the professional competence of an up-to-date specialist.

The problem of creative development of the individual in the learning process is an urgent scientific problem now. Creative activity of a person elaborates something new, whether it is something of the external world or a well-known structure of mind or feelings that live and appear only in the person. From the point of view of philosophy, creativity also generates new values, ideas, and the person himself as a creator becomes different in his development [7, 85].

When considering the process of learning at the university, the concept of creativity is associated with the concept of independence, which is considered as the quality of a person, reflecting their ability to self-regulate thinking and determining the effectiveness of performing professional duties. Considering its importance for professional development of future young specialists, independent creative activity of the student acquires a special status in the practice of teaching in higher educational institutions and is of particular importance in planning the educational programs. Creative types of educational activities give students an additional incentive to improve themselves as future professionals, learn to independently search for new knowledge in various situations, as well as see a new problem in the trivial situation, form their vision, their attitude towards it and offer their own way of solving it. Formation of these particular skills should become an obligatory element of professional training of a modern specialist [7, 86–87].

It should be noted that organizing and conducting creative educational events together with potential employers stimulates students' motivation and effectively prepares them for future professional activities. Future employers, in turn, have an opportunity to identify the most active and capable students, assess their potential in order to support and help them start their professional activities on the basis of their enterprises and organizations. For example, effective educational activities are joint organization of various forms of educational activities by teachers and employers, such as lectures, seminars, round-tables, master classes by employers of enterprises – practitioners in their fields, organization of student competitions in conjunction with representatives of enterprises and companies. Also, other possible forms of cooperation between universities and employers are [3, 15–16]:

- joint laboratories of educational institutions and companies;
- additional optional courses with invited industry professionals;
- branches of departments on the basis of enterprises and companies;
- participation of companies and enterprises in professional training and retraining of teachers;
- participation of teachers and employers in thematic conferences held on the basis of enterprises and universities;
- holding job fairs;
- practice and internship of students at enterprises;
- professional study tours of junior students to enterprises.

So, IT companies have been actively participating in the training of future specialists for their industry for several years. Employees of the companies conduct lectures and seminars on key topics of training future IT specialists. Also, the companies, in cooperation with the university, pay special attention to improving the level of English proficiency of IT-students.

As an example, we can mention English testing. The content of the tests can be compiled jointly by teachers and employers with the aim of maximally approximating their content to the functions of using a foreign language in future professional activities. Since, basically, for professional activity of a programmer the skills of spoken English and listening are necessary, therefore, the content of such tests includes the verification of these linguistic aspects. Students who won prizes based on testing results are awarded certificates from an IT company, which provide them with additional employment opportunities. Thus, the company at an early stage of study in the university can select capable and motivated students, and together with their teachers prepare them for future professional activities, thereby significantly fostering their motivation in learning.

To improve the quality of training and, at the same time, to develop and encourage students' creative potential different contests of educational projects can be offered. To prepare for such a contest, students, together with teachers, prepare educational projects in English on actual topics of IT industry and present

them to the competition jury, which consists of company employees. Based on the results of the presentation and interviews in English with the representatives of the jury, company representatives single out the best works and reward the winners with preference when applying for a job in the company.

The possible scheme for organizing the teacher's independent creative activity of students in preparation for the competition of educational projects can be the following [7, 88–89]:

1. Initial stage. The teacher and student together choose and discuss a topic in the context of the general theme of the competition. The teacher focuses on the content and structure of the project, recommends sources and literature for preparation, stipulates the terms and schedule for the preparation of the project. The student acts in accordance with the designated assignment schedule.

2. Advanced stage. The teacher provides advisory support, corrects and directs the research, controls intermediate results. The student independently fills the content of the project, structures the material, chooses the presentation format and visualization method.

3. The final stage. It is characterized by the freedom to realize the student's creative potential, which manifests itself in the creative presentation of the results of his research, in the choice of the most effective form of his presentation to the audience. The instructor advises and is the first spectator for the student.

To prepare a university graduate for future production activities, it is necessary to intensify the practice of inviting practitioners to give lectures and conduct seminars, round-tables, which will be able to familiarize students with the specifics of activities in a particular industry and at specific enterprises. In order to develop the students' professional competence, as well as to develop professionally oriented foreign language competence, seminars can be organized in English with the participation of representatives of the industrial enterprises. Participants have the opportunity to present in English their enterprises and areas of activity to students. Students have the opportunity to communicate online in English with speakers and clarify questions of interest to them on the operation of enterprises, production and employment opportunities. Such events arouse significant interest not only among students and teachers of the university, but are also of interest to the participants themselves who can act as mentors in the university environment.

To train young specialists, universities constantly monitor current professions of the labor market, qualifications in demand, modern employers' requirements for the professional competencies of university graduates. The higher education system cannot instantly respond to the ongoing changes; therefore, universities monitor the labor market conditions in advance, the balance of supply and demand, and carry out short-term and long-term forecasts of transformations in the labor market.

Being aware of the changes in the labor market is very important for the universities. Thus, universities can react with the introduction of new specialties, correct the educational process and adapt it to the ongoing changes. So, in order to interact with employers, universities can hold conferences and round-table discussions. In such conferences the representatives of government bodies in different areas, representatives of industrial enterprises, IT companies, sports and cultural organizations, secondary education institutions can be participants. The reports of the participants can be presented, topical issues of training specialists at the university and their relevance for employers are discussed.

Universities conduct different surveys of the representatives of the labor market in order to monitor their position on training specialists at the university and the possibilities of their direct participation in the educational process. The questionnaire can include such questions as:

1. Is the work being carried out to form a personnel reserve for specialist positions in enterprises among university graduates?

2. How is the work held with the students who are sent by higher education institutions for internship in the organization?

3. Does the organization need a scientific study of the problematic aspects of management in the framework of the implementation by students of higher education institutions of course and diploma (master's) work on the relevant topic?

4. Does the organization participate in arranging an order for the specialists who are trained in higher education institutions?

5. In the training (retraining) of what specialists does the organization have the need today, connected with the profile of higher education institution?

6. In what forms of organization are they ready to participate in the educational process?

7. Select specialties that, in your opinion, will be in demand in organizations in 4–8 years, etc.

The results of the survey of employers can be used for adjusting the educational process at the universities, for as well as in further interaction to implement a close relationship among students, teachers and employers.

As examples of creative forms of educational activity in foreign language classes, we can cite the dramatization of culture-oriented role-playing games. These techniques are tools for the development of speech skills in practice of intercultural communication, but also involve the creative use of communicative competence by students for the successful fulfillment of the declared communicative role. A culturally oriented role-playing game is a «problem-communicative foreign language task that creates educational and

methodological conditions for social-speech modeling of role positions (indicated in these tasks) by trainees, taking into account the functional factors of foreign and intercultural communication, as well as the sociocultural background of role situations and prescriptions or expectations in the process of jointly solving socially and professionally significant communicative tasks» [5]. All structural components of such a game (the goal of the game, the content of the game, the totality of social roles, the conditions for implementation) are formulated and presented in such a way as to orient students towards the culture of the country of the target language, immersing them in the socio-cultural context of a foreign language linguistic culture. Unlike other tasks, culture-oriented role-playing games not only develop speaking skills, but also teach them to use their cultural knowledge in interaction.

The main component of a culture-oriented role-playing game, like any role-playing game, is a role, namely a set of social and interpersonal roles, the performance of which by trainees involves them in the process of communication and mastering communication [1]. Fulfilling various roles (status, positional, situational), the student learns to follow a specific communication program, choose adequate language means, vary behavior strategies and show communicative flexibility in order to justify the "role expectations" of the speech behavior of the native speaker of the target language in such situations. In the process of completing the task, the student develops socio-cultural abilities and fosters the socio-cultural qualities necessary for effective intercultural communication. In a culture-oriented role-playing game, social relations existing in a society are reproduced, which forces the participants to comply with certain rules and conditions of the game, following the norms of foreign language communicative behavior. The coincidence of role prescriptions existing in a foreign language linguaculture with role expectations of certain speech behavior is an indicator that the student is able to carry out effective intercultural communication with a native speaker of the target language.

The content of culture-oriented games is determined both by the subject of the course and by a specific goal. Let us give examples of the subject of culture-oriented role-playing games [4, 96–97]. So, to develop students' ability to establish and maintain communicative contact, the culture-oriented role-playing games «Let's get to know each other» can be used: two strangers (Belarusian and American), who are forced to sit at the same table in a crowded cafe, start a conversation. Culturally oriented role-playing games «My personal space» can be used to develop the ability to maintain the proper distance with a native speaker of the target language. For example, during the conversation, your longtime friend asks a lot of personal questions. To develop the ability to create a positive microclimate of interaction using the strategy of communicative self-presentation, the culture-oriented role-playing games «The Art of self-presentation» are effective, which involve dramatizing such a plot as: Your friend won an international competition and you express your praise to him, emphasizing the positive aspects of the performance.

Thus, the activation of vocationally-oriented education at the university, implemented in close cooperation between universities and enterprises provide a close relationship and consistency of the educational process with the requirements of the labor market, teachers and employers, and is aimed at training highly qualified young professionals.

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СУЧАСНІ ТЕНДЕНЦІЇ ВИКЛАДАННЯ ІНОЗЕМНОЇ МОВИ В УНІВЕРСИТЕТІ

Мета статті – обґрунтувати значення і розглянути шляхи впровадження професійно орієнтованої освіти загалом та на прикладі викладання іноземної мови як не основної спеціальності зокрема. Однією з цілей є показати варіанти взаємодії університету та роботодавців для підвищення ефективності підготовки сучасних спеціалістів як за основною спеціальністю, так і з іноземної мови.

Методологія. Наводяться конкретні приклади різних професійно орієнтованих заходів, які можна організувати спільно з потенційними роботодавцями, за їх безпосередньої участі в навчальному процесі. Детально розглядаються такі форми роботи, як: тестування, конкурси освітніх проєктів, англомовні семінари, анкети роботодавців, заняття іноземною мовою, які необхідні для навчання студентів впровадження ділової міжкультурної комунікації у майбутній професійній діяльності.

Наукова новизна. Розглядаються методи організації професійно орієнтованих заходів іноземною мовою, які є ефективними інструментами іншомовної професійної підготовки студентів. Особливістю цих заходів є спільна організація та реалізація цих форм роботи викладачами та потенційними роботодавцями. Безпосередня участь потенційних роботодавців у професійній підготовці студентів є потужним стимулом для студентів і сприяє більш ефективному професійному навчанню та вивченню іноземних мов.

Висновки. Для роботодавців на сучасному етапі важливо, щоб молоді спеціалісти не лише знали основи своєї професії, але й мали нові навички й уміння, які доповнюють професійну компетентність фахівця. Розвиток у студентів таких умінь, що користуються попитом на ринку праці, вимагає нестандартного підходу до організації навчальних занять та різноманітних навчальних заходів. Ці заходи активізують творчі здібності та мислення студентів, розвивають уміння самостійного пошуку унікальних рішень, мотивують до вивчення іноземних мов і є невід'ємними складовими професійної компетентності сучасного фахівця. Активізація професійно-орієнтованого навчання в університеті забезпечує тісний взаємозв'язок і відповідність навчального процесу вимогам ринку праці та спрямована на підготовку висококваліфікованих молодих спеціалістів.

Ключові слова: університет, ринок праці, роботодавці, професійна підготовка, культурно-орієнтовані завдання.

Стаття надійшла до редакції 22.10.2020

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